

Authorization from Schools for Data Collection

I, _____, director
of the School _____

(INEP Code: _____) located at

authorize the collection of data from the Anonymous project of the Anonymous
Institution on the school environment. I am aware that this project is authorized by the
Certificate of Presentation of Ethical Appreciation (CAAE) number
*****.*.****.****.